

Dual-vat photopolymerization 3D printing of vitrimers

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Abstract

Vitrimers undergo stimuli-triggered bond exchange reactions, which render the covalently cross-linked networks malleable, repairable and recyclable. While additive manufacturing with single vitrimeric materials has become a well-established strategy for fabricating objects with unique functions, 3D printing of vitrimers with heterogeneous and locally controllable material properties is still in its infancy. Herein, the processing of multi-material vitrimers is demonstrated with a dual-vat digital light processing (DLP) 3D printer. The printer prototype contains two vats and a cleaning station, which are positioned on a linearly moving platform, and are exchanged automatically during the layer-by-layer build-up of the object. Two thiol-acrylate resins are selected containing ample -OH and ester moieties, which undergo thermo-activated transesterification in the presence of an organic phosphate as catalyst. Once cured, the photopolymers greatly differ in their mechanical properties allowing the printing of multi-material structures with soft ($E'_{23^\circ\text{C}} = 209$ kPa) and stiff ($E'_{23^\circ\text{C}} = 507$ MPa) domains. A good interlayer adhesion between the soft and hard domains is evidenced by uniaxial tensile tests, whilst optical microscopy is used to study the interface. Jacobs working curves of the two different resins reveal comparable printing parameters at higher exposure doses, which do not only facilitate the printing of multiple materials between individual layers (z-heterogeneity) but also within the same layer (x,y-heterogeneity). This is confirmed by the printing of a multi-material gripper, which contains soft inner teeth and a stiff outer core. Gripping and releasing of objects is demonstrated by exploiting the glass transition-based shape memory properties of the stiff domains. Moreover, due to the dynamic nature of the covalent bonds, damages inserted into the gripper are intrinsically repairable due to a thermo-activated macroscopic reflow. Shape memory experiments further confirmed that the multi-material gripper fully regains its function after the thermal mending process. Thus, the results clearly show that objects with a high degree of functionality can be realized by combining multi-material 3D printing with the chemistry of vitrimers. This is of particular interest for future soft robotic applications and for mimicking biological composite structures.

Key words: dual-vat photopolymerization 3D printing, multi-material, vitrimers, photopolymers, soft active devices

1. Introduction

By being able to undergo stimuli-triggered bond exchange reactions, vitrimers behave like permanently crosslinked duromers (under specific conditions), while they become reprocessable/weldable as a thermoplastic once the underlying chemical reaction is activated.[1,2] The related change in the viscosity and material flow is an unprecedented feature of vitrimers and its control is crucial for future technical applications.[3–7] To avoid creep, the bond exchange reactions should be inactive (or the exchange rate sufficiently slow) during operation of the polymer part. However, once the material is exposed to an appropriate stimulus (typically heat), efficient bond exchange reactions are activated, and the related material's flow should render the network reprocessable[8,9], mendable[10,11], and repairable.[12,13]

As the flow capacity of a vitrimer and the temperature onset for exchange reactions are governed by the mobility of the relevant functional groups[14], crosslink density[15], kinetics[16] and thermodynamic equilibrium[17] of the bond exchange reactions, numerous reversible mechanisms and synthesis strategies can be found in literature.[18] Among the various bond exchange mechanisms, the thermo-activated transesterification is highly popular as it is not prone to side reaction and building blocks from both petrol-based and bio-based resources are readily available.[19]

Additive manufacturing of vitrimers following a thermo-activated exchange between hydroxy and ester groups has been well described in literature and has been used for the fabrication soft active devices with additional functions such as recyclability[20,21], repairability[22,23] and malleability[24]. Vat photopolymerization is often applied, as this type of 3D printing technique offers several advantages by being relatively cheap, fast and precise in the production of objects with a high level of complexity in their designed shapes.[25] In vat photopolymerization 3D printing the object is formed by a point-wise (stereolithography) or layer-wise (digital light processing, DLP) solidification of a resin formulation by light exposure.

Zhang and co-workers reported on the DLP 3D printing of acrylate-based vitrimers containing hydroxyl ester moieties, which underwent thermo-activated transesterification in the presence of an organic zinc salt as catalyst.[26] With the same network architecture, Li et al. 3D printed objects with high resolution and discussed possible upcycling routes by exploiting the dynamic nature of the hydroxyl ester bonds.[27] By introducing organic phosphates as versatile and efficient transesterification catalysts, our group demonstrated the DLP 3D printing of dynamic acrylate and thiol-click photopolymers.[28–30] With a dual-wavelength DLP 3D printer operating with two different LEDs, we were further able to locally activate the

transesterification catalyst during the printing process.[31,32] Intrinsically healable soft active devices were manufactured, whose shape memory properties and malleability could be varied depending on the light source used during the layer-by-layer printing.

However, whilst DLP 3D printing of single materials has been well established for vitrimers, the fabrication of multi-material structures with dynamic covalent bonds is still under explored. Multi-material 3D printing offers the ability to integrate materials with different chemical, mechanical, electrical or optical properties in one object and is employed for the manufacture of complex structures used in tissue engineering[33], drug delivery[34], soft robotics[35] or electronics.[36] In vat photopolymerization 3D printing, multi-material properties can be realized by varying the intensity during printing (grey scale printing), changing the color/wavelength of the LED lamp or by changing the vat.[37]

Boydston and co-workers used grayscale imaging to print heterogeneous objects from acrylate-based systems. Depending on the light intensity, they were able to control the crosslink density and related mechanical properties in a localized manner.[38] They further used sequence dependent orthogonal photoreactions in epoxy-acrylate hybrid resins to print soft and stiff domains by switching the LEDs (405 and 365 nm) during the printing process.[39] Upon 405 nm irradiation, the acrylate groups were selectively cured and subsequent UV exposure induced the curing of the epoxy monomers. Due to the higher crosslink density, the formed interpenetrating network showed a distinctive increase in stiffness. In a follow-up study, we improved build speed and toughness of the printed parts by optimizing the resin formulation and using a new dual-wavelength printer.[40]

Another strategy for the fabrication of multi-material objects by vat photopolymerization 3D printing is based on a material exchange between different resin vats[41] using a rotational platform[42] or a delivery system with microfluidic inks.[43] Typically a cleaning step is required to remove un-reacted resin from the object and to avoid a cross-contamination of the different vats. This cleaning step significantly slows down the build speed. Matte and co-workers developed a multi-material DLP setup with an automated storage and retrieval system.[44] In their tower approach, they provided up to eight vats as vertical trays. In comparison to rotary systems, the time delays during vat exchange could be significantly reduced due to the vertical arrangement. For a fast exchange of materials, Kowsari et al. deposited resin droplets via syringes on a glass plate layer-by-layer during the printing process.[45] To meet the designed layer thickness, the printing platform was adjusted above the glass plate leaving an appropriate gap for the resin.

Herein, we use a new dual-vat DLP printer relying on an automatic exchange of vats for the multi-material 3D printing of vitrimers. By using previously explored thiol-acrylate vitrimers, [15] we were able to produce soft ($E'_{23^\circ\text{C}} = 209$ kPa) and stiff ($E'_{23^\circ\text{C}} = 507$ MPa) networks by varying the monomer composition. The printing and intrinsic healing of functional devices with locally controlled heterogeneity and shape memory properties along the three axis is demonstrated, giving rise to the versatility of the multi-material 3D printed vitrimers.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 Network design and printing of single material structures

For the dual-vat DLP 3D printing of vitrimers, two different thiol-acrylate photopolymers were chosen, which varied significantly in their thermal and mechanical properties (**Table 1**). In particular, the soft EGMA-HP1A with a glass transition temperature (T_g) of 3°C , and the stiff EGMA-PT3A with a T_g above room temperature (50°C). The storage modulus at 23°C ($E'_{23^\circ\text{C}}$) of the two resins varied over several orders of magnitude and amounted to 209 kPa and 507 MPa for EGMA-HP1A and EGMA-PT3A, respectively (DMA curves are provided in **Figure 1c** and **d**). As shown in previous work, the resins benefit from fast cure kinetics, low viscosity and prolonged shelf life, which make them ideal materials for vat photopolymerization 3D printing.[15] In their cured state, both photopolymers comprised ample -OH groups (via the multi-functional acrylates HP1A and DG2A) and ester moieties, which were able to undergo transesterification at elevated temperature. The kinetics of the bond exchange reactions were significantly accelerated by adding an organic phosphate as transesterification catalyst. Due to their difference in network structure, mobility and availability of functional groups, the two photopolymers under investigation exhibited different stress relaxation kinetics. By keeping the EGMA-HP1A and EGMA-PT3A at 180°C , the normalized modulus ($G(t)/G_0$) reached 37% of its initial value (τ^*) after 8.8 and 83.5 min respectively (**Figure S1** in supporting information).

Table 1. Mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties of the thiol-acrylate photopolymers used in the dual-wavelength DLP 3D printing process and thermally annealed at 180°C (4 h).

Formulation	T_g [$^\circ\text{C}$]	$E'_{(23^\circ\text{C})}$ [MPa]	σ [MPa]	ε [%]	E_T [MPa]	τ^* [min]
EGMA-HP1A	3	0.2	1.1 ± 0.1	14.0 ± 1.1	9.0 ± 0.4	8.8
EGMA-PT3A	50	507.0	33.3 ± 0.3	4.4 ± 0.1	1472 ± 25	83.5

Along with stress relaxation, the thermal treatment at 180°C also led to a distinctive increase in the samples' toughness, which is related to topological rearrangements of the network,

hydrogen bonding and additional formation of covalent crosslinks. Thus, in the current study, all printed objects were treated at 180 °C for 4 h prior to any further measurements unless otherwise noted.

Multi-material printing experiments were carried out with a dual-vat DLP prototype, which was manufactured by way2production GmbH. The printer contained a high intensity (max. 40 mW/cm²) light engine from In-Vision Digital Imaging Optics GmbH operating at 405 nm with a pixel size of 50 μm. The light engine was fixed in its position, whilst the two vats together with cleaning station were positioned on a linearly sliding platform. During printing the multi-material test structures, the platform was raised automatically to a safe distance in z-direction (70 mm above zero-point), once the defined material layer(s) were deposited on the build platform. Subsequently, the vat was exchanged with the cleaning station, which consisted of a dry sponge. For the cleaning, the platform was adjusted in such a way that the built object was pressed to the surface of the sponge. After pressing the sponge at a depth of 10 mm, the platform was sheared 25 mm in x- and y-direction to mechanically remove uncured resin residues. The platform was then raised up again (70 mm above zero-point) and the second resin vat was moved into the printing position. The whole process was continued until the required number of layers and the multi-material design was fully printed. Each vat could be heated up to 70 °C but in the present study, the multi-material 3D-printing was carried out at room temperature, with a layer thickness of 100 μm and by using a rising and retracting speed of 5 mm/s.

The optimum layer cure time (10-12 s) was obtained from the Jacobs working curves of EGMA-HP1A and EGMA-PT3A, since the two materials show similar curing depths in this region (see **Figure S2** in supporting information). For this, single material discs ($d = 10$ mm) were printed at different irradiation times whilst keeping the light intensity constant (10 mW/cm²). Following the Jacobs equation, the thickness of the cured layer was plotted against the exposure dose. From the results it can be seen that the curing depths become more comparable with increasing exposure dose. Therefore, the optimum layer cure time was set to 10-12 s to achieve not only good printability, but also sufficient interfacial adhesion.

To visualize the difference in the single materials' mechanical properties hollow circular test structures ($d = 30$ mm, $h = 2$ mm) were 3D-printed using either EGMA-PT3A or EGMA-HP1A. The printed objects were placed in a hydraulic press and deformed (**Figure 1e** and **f**). The stiff EGMA-PT3A photopolymer was not able to undergo large deformation and rapidly broke under compression, whilst the soft EGMA-HP1A was flexible enough that the circular test structure could be nearly fully compressed until failure was observed.

Figure 1. (a) Photograph and (d) schematic representation of the multi-material DLP 3D printer prototype comprised of two vats and a cleaning positioned on a linearly moving platform and a fixed light engine. Storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of resin (c) EGMA-HP1A and (d) EGMA-PT3A versus temperature. DLP 3D printed single material objects with varying stiffness, which is reflected by the different compression behavior of the test specimen: (e) EGMA-HP1A and (f) EGMA-PT3A. The scale bar is 20 mm.

2.2 Multi-material DLP 3D printing experiments

In the first step, a double wheel structure ($d = 42$ mm, $h = 2$ mm) was manufactured. The inner supporting circle ($d = 20$ mm) was printed with the stiff EGMA-PT3A (**Figure 2a**), whilst for the outer circle with connecting arcs the soft EGMA-HP1A was used. Due to the comparable cure behavior of the resins (and thus obtained layer thickness upon 10 s light exposure), it was possible to print multiple material domains in the x-,y-plane. Under compression, the soft domains (EGMA-HP1A) could be deformed without any damage, and multiple compression and retraction cycles could be undertaken by the wheel (**Figure 2b**). During these tests, the hard-inner ring (EGMA-PT3A) remained intact and maintained its structural function without undergoing any deformation. Such a structure mimics the functional traits of an automobile wheel, where the inner metal part provides structural strength while the soft elastomeric tire provides shock absorption and damping.[46]

Figure 2. (a) CAD design of a double-wheel structure containing an inner ring (grey) made from the stiff EGMA-PT3A photopolymer, and the outer ring and connecting arcs (turquoise) based on the soft EGMA-HP1A network. (b) Sequence of the compression and decompression of the double-wheel structure in a hydraulic press. (c) Multi-material honeycomb structure DLP 3D printed with EGMA-PT3A (orange) and EGMA-HP1A (dark red). (d) Shape memory experiments involving the programming at -10 °C for 20 min and the shape recovery at room temperature.

To demonstrate the printing of more complex multi-material objects, a honeycomb structure was DLP 3D-printed (**Figure 2c**). The outer parts of the honeycomb were printed with the stiff EGMA-PT3A (orange) to provide structural integrity, whilst the inner combs were printed with the soft EGMA-HP1A (dark red). From optical microscopy images it was obtained that the

thickness of the honeycomb struts amounted to around 400 μm (**Figure S3** in supporting information). Shape memory experiments were then performed on the printed structure by compressing it along its y-axis (at room temperature) and fixing the temporary shape by placing the deformed object in a deep freezer at $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min. Full shape recovery was obtained within 60 s after heating the programmed structure to room temperature (**Figure 2d**).

As the pronounced mismatch in stiffness may lead to stress concentrations at the interface,[47] the interlayer adhesion between EGMA-HP1A and EGMA-PT3A was studied. For this, heterogeneous dumbbell shaped test specimen, in which one half of the sample was printed with EGMA-HP1A and the other half with EGMA-PT3A (inset in **Figure 3**), were fabricated. Uniaxial tensile tests were performed with digital image correlation using Mercury DIC System software. Here, the camera monitored the deformation of the samples during the tensile tests. The results were then compared with test specimen fully printed with the single materials. To evaluate the influence of thermo-activated bond exchange reactions across the interface between EGMA-HP1A and EGMA-PT3A-based domains, the stress-strain curves were measured prior to and after thermal annealing at $180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 h (**Figure 3**). It should be noted that the tensile properties differ from the results reported in our previous study as we were using different sample geometry, printer and printing parameters.[15]

Figure 3. Stress strain curves of homogeneously and heterogeneously (on half was printed with EGMA-HP1A and the other half with EGMA-PT3A) DLP 3D printed test specimen. The samples were tested prior to (full lines) and after (dashed lines) a thermal annealing at $180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 h. Inset depicts a photograph of the 3D printed test specimens.

The thermal treatment leads to a distinctive rise in tensile strength and stiffness of EGMA-PT3A networks, whilst for EGMA-HP1A, the increase is less pronounced. The change in the mechanical properties is mainly related to hydrogen bonding, additional formation of irreversible bonds between unreacted acrylate groups and thermo-activated topological rearrangement in the photopolymers. Independent on the thermal treatment, the tensile strength of the multi-material structure is comparable to the soft EGMA-HP1A network whilst ultimate elongation is significantly lower. However, all tested multi-material samples showed cohesive failure in the soft EGMA-HP1A domain (**Figure S4** in supporting information and **video S1**). On the one hand, this indicates a good interlayer adhesion between the two selected thiol-acrylate photopolymers. On the other hand, a possible effect of the thermo-activated bond exchange reactions on interphase strength could not be confirmed with the tensile data. Via optical microscopy the interface between stiff (EGMA-PT3A) and soft (EGMA-HP1A) domains and the effect of a thermal annealing step was investigated. Thus, circles ($d = 10\text{ mm}$) were printed, half of which consisted of the stiff material and the other half of the soft material. The width of the interface was determined directly after printing and after an additional thermal treatment (4 h at $180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). As expected, the annealing step resulted in reducing the width by half (from $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to $50\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) based on thermo-activated bond exchange reactions and the related macroscopic reflow of the two dynamic photopolymer networks (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4. Optical micrographs of the interface between soft and stiff domains (a) directly after printing and (b) after thermal annealing ($180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 h).

2.3 Multi-material DLP 3D printing of thermally mendable soft active devices

Advancing from proof of concept studies, a multi-material gripper was printed, which was comprised of a stiff half circle (EGMA-PT3A) equipped with inner teeth made of the soft EGMA-HP1A for handling delicate objects. To evaluate its gripping abilities, a strawberry was chosen as a natural object that is easily damaged during pick-up and release. The programming of the gripper was performed by heating the object at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is above the T_g of EGMA-

PT3A. By applying an external force, the gripper was compressed in x-direction from the original width of 42 mm to 26 mm. With this set-up, the device gripped and lifted the strawberry in the programmed shape, which was fixed by cooling the gripper to room temperature (**Figure 5b**). Heating the gripper again above the T_g of the stiff network with a heat gun led to a fast shape recovery and release of the strawberry (**Figure 5c and g**).

Figure 5. (a) CAD design of the multi-material gripper containing soft teeth (grey) positioned on a stiff half circle (turquoise). (b) Programming the temporary shape by heating the printed gripper to 60 °C and cooling it in the deformed state to room temperature. (c) Picking a strawberry during the programming step and releasing the object by heating the gripper above 60 °C with a heat gun. Multi-material gripper (d) prior to and (e) after thermal healing (180 °C, 4 h). (f) Programming and (g) shape recovery of the healed gripper.

Owing to their dynamic bonds, the thiol-acrylate photopolymers possess the exceptional ability to macroscopically reflow at a sufficiently high temperature, which can be exploited to intrinsically heal damages inserted into the multi-material 3D printed structure. To demonstrate the healability, a part of the multi-material gripper was cut off using a sharp blade (**Figure 5d**). For the healing step, the damaged sections were joined physically, aligned and placed between two glass plates. A pressure was then applied by placing two weights (400 g each) on top (**Figure S5** in supporting information) and thermally annealing the set-up in an oven at 180 °C for 4 h. Due to the efficient transesterifications and related topological rearrangement, the damaged section was fully healed after thermal treatment and the healed gripper regained its gripping function as demonstrated by subsequent shape memory experiments (**Figure 5e**). In this experiment, it was possible to program the healed gripper to the same deformed form (26

mm) as of the original one (**Figure 5g**). Furthermore, the healed gripper was also able to carry the weight of the strawberry and release it by thermally triggered shape recovery.

3. Conclusion

Multi-material 3D printing of vitrimeric photopolymers was realized by using a dual-vat DLP 3D printer containing two automatically exchangeable vats and a cleaning station. With this printing set-up, the integration of more than one material along all three axes is quite challenging to achieve. However, in the present study, the two selected thiol-acrylate resins provided comparable curing depths at higher exposure doses, which enabled multi-material fabrication within both individual layers (z-heterogeneity) and the same layer (x,y-heterogeneity). This offered a higher degree of freedom in the design of objects, as the material properties could not be only changed along the z-axis but also in the x,y-plane. In addition, the printed objects benefited from a strong interlayer adhesion between soft and stiff domains, whose storage modulus varied over several order of magnitude. Optical microscopy further revealed a high resolution of the multi-material domains, which offers the possibility to print composite structures mimicking biological structures in future work. The ability to introduce stiffness variations in macroscopic soft active devices was demonstrated by the 3D printing of a multi-material gripper, which underwent T_g-based programming and shape recovery. Once damaged, the gripper recovered its function after intrinsic healing by exploiting the macroscopic reflow which was induced by thermo-activated bond exchange reactions.

Summing up, dual-vat 3D printing with vitrimers is a versatile approach to easily fabricate functional devices with multi-material properties, and a broad range of material properties can be covered by using commercially available initiators and resins.

4. Experimental Part

4.1 Material and Chemicals

2-Hydroxy-3-phenoxy propyl acrylate (HP1A), glycerol 1,3-diglycerolate diacrylate (DG2A), 1,6 hexane dithiol (HXDT), trimethylolpropane triacrylate (PT3A), phenylbis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (Irgacure 819) and Mordant Blue were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Ethylene glycol bis(3-mercaptopropionate) (EGMP) was kindly provided by Bruno Bock Chemische Fabrik (Germany), Miramer A99 was supplied by Miwon Specialty Chemicals (Korea) and Sudan II was from TCI chemicals (Tokyo, Japan). All chemicals were used as received and without further purification.

4.2 Preparation of photocurable formulation

The composition of the photocurable thiol-acrylate resins, which was taken from literature, is shown in **Table 2**. [15] The formulations were prepared according to the previously published protocol, in which all components were placed in light-protected glass vials and mixed by means of a magnetic stirrer at room temperature for 1 h.

Table 2. Composition of thiol-acrylate resins under investigation.

Formulation	HP1A [mol%]	PT3A [mol%]	GD2A [mol%]	Irgacure 819 [wt%]	Mirammer A99 [wt%]	Mordant Blue [wt%]	Sudan II [wt%]
EGMA-HP1A	50		25	2	10	0.05	-
EGMA-PT3A ²	-	50	25	2	10	-	0.05

4.3 Jacobs working curve

The Jacobs working curve was obtained from EGMA-HP1A and EGMA-PT3A according to literature. [48] For the experiments, one-layer discs with a diameter of 10 mm were cured with the dual-vat printer at varying exposure times (2 - 18 s). The intensity of the light engine was kept constant at 10 mW.cm⁻². Once printed, the specimens were rinsed with isopropanol to remove any non-cured liquid resin residues and the thickness of the printed samples was determined with a thickness gauge. For each setting, two samples were measured and the arithmetic average was taken for determining the working curve with the following equation:

$$C_d = D_p \cdot \ln \left(\frac{E_{max}}{E_c} \right)$$

in which C_d (μm) corresponds to the cured depth/thickness of the sample and E_{max} (mJ cm^{-2}) to the light energy of the incident light on the surface. E_c (mJ cm^{-2}) corresponds to the exposure dose of the gel point (transition from liquid to solid state) and D_p (μm) is the penetration depth of the incident light. By plotting C_d versus E_{max} in a semilogarithmic way a linear curve (Jacobs working curve) is obtained, from which E_c is taken from the interception of the Jacobs working curve with the x-axis and D_p from its slope.

4.4 Dual-vat DLP 3D printing

Multi-material DLP 3D printing was performed on a dual-vat DLP prototype, which was manufactured by way2production (Austria). The building area of the printer was 67.2 x 37.8 x 130.0 mm with a maximum filling of 210 mL of each vat. The layer thickness could be varied between 25 and 200 μm . The vat could be heated up to 70 °C, but in the current study the

printing was carried out at room temperature. The DLP printer operated with a light engine from In-Vision Digital Imaging Optics GmbH operating at 405 nm (max. 40 mW/cm²) with a pixel size of 50 μm. Both soft and stiff resin were printed with a layer thickness of 100 μm and a rising and retracting speed of 5 mm/s. The bottom layer was exposed for 15 s and the subsequent layers for 10 s. The multi-material printed objects were rinsed with isopropanol to remove non-reacted monomers from the surface and were post-baked at 120 °C for 4 h, unless otherwise stated.

4.5 Characterization of thermomechanical and mechanical properties

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed on a Mettler Toledo DMA/SDTA861e analyser. Mechanical loss factors (tan delta) and storage moduli (E') were measured between -50 and 100 °C at a heating rate of 3 °C/min, with a frequency of 1 Hz, maximum displacement of 3 μm and maximum force of 8 N. The T_g was determined by the temperature at the maximum of the loss factor. Single material test specimen (35 mm x 7 mm x 22 mm) were fabricated by dual-vat DLP 3D printing.

Stress-strain curves were obtained with an Instron 5500 (Instron, DEU) Universal Tester, using a 100 N load cell, pneumatic foil grips and a test speed of 1 mm/min. Dog bone-shaped samples (2 mm x 12 mm x 0.1 mm) were DLP 3D printed according to ISO 527 type 5B. Tensile testing was carried out at 23 °C (50% RH) with digital image correlation employing a Mercury DIC System (software version 2.8), a UI-3180CP-M-GL R2.1 camera, and a Componon-S 2.8/50 lens (Schneider Kreuznach, DEU). The gauge length of the extensometer amounted to 10 mm.

4.6 Optical microscopy

The multi-material 3D printed honeycomb structure was studied with a BX 51 optical microscope from Olympus (Japan) and images were taken with a Colour View IIIu digital camera (Soft Imaging System, Germany).

4.7 Shape memory and intrinsic healing

Shape memory and thermal healing experiments were performed on various multi-material DLP 3D printed structures. Initial experiments were performed on a honeycomb structure (29 mm x 25 mm x 4 mm), with soft struts printed with EGMA-HP1A sandwiched by stiff (EGMA-PT3A) honeycombs. For programming the structure was compressed along its y-axis at room temperature and placed in the deformed shape in a deep freezer at -10 °C for 20 min. For shape

recovery, the structure was removed from the freezer and kept at room temperature until full shape recovery (60 s).

For shape memory experiments on the multi-material gripper, the printed structure was heated to 60 °C and compressed along the y-axis. The programmed shape was fixed by a cooling the deformed structure to room temperature. The gripper was then heated with a heat gun and the original shape was recovered within 30 s.

Thermal healing experiments were performed on the same multi-material gripper, from which a part was cut at an angle of 45° using a sharp knife. The damaged parts of the sample were brought together and aligned to ensure a proper contact of the damaged surfaces. The gripper was then pressed between two glass plates under a weight of 800 g and heated in an oven at 180 °C for 4 h. Once healed, shape memory experiments were repeated as described above to evaluate the functionality of the repaired gripper.

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